

ANALYSIS OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES IN UNABI FRUITS

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ABSTRACT

The conducted studies revealed varietal differences and limits for the accumulation of flavonols (8.6–17.5 mg/100 g), amino acids (184.7–491.2 mg/100 g), and macro and microelements in Unabi fruits. Unabi varieties with a high content of biologically active substances in their fruits were studied. Vitamin C "Jishin-zao," "Shiyang-zao," and "Jun-zao"; Vitamin P (catechins) in "Jishin-zao" and "Jun-zao"; leucoanthocyanins in "Jun-zao" and "Zanghuang-da-zao"; The amino acids "Jun-zao," "Shiyang-zao," and "Tang-zao"; Minerals were found in the "Jishin-zao" and "Jun-zao" varieties.

Introduction. Unabi fruits possess a unique composition of natural antioxidants, making them not only beneficial for human consumption but also a promising raw material for industry.

There is a lot of information in scientific sources that Unabi fruits are a source of important microelements. This necessitates the consumption of fresh fruits while preserving their therapeutic and prophylactic properties due to their high vitamin, amino acid, and mineral content. Therefore, it is necessary to develop systematic storage technologies to provide the population with unabi fruits throughout the year[1].

In recent years, when assessing the nutritional status of consumers, significant changes in the composition of food have been observed, leading to imbalances in the main dietary components: insufficient intake of natural proteins, vitamins, macro and microelements, and, conversely, excessive intake of animal fats and simple carbohydrates[2]. One way to optimize nutrition is to increase the proportion of fresh fruits and vegetables in the diet as a source of natural biologically active substances. [3,4].

Object and methods of research: As the object of research, 10 different varieties of unabi fruits grown in the experimental farm of the Tashkent State Agrarian University were used. Vitamin C - using the accelerated method according to A.I. Yermakov; R-active substances using the vanillin method modified by L.I. Vigorova; The composition of organic and amino acids, as well as mineral substances, was studied using the capillary electrophoresis method in "Kapel 104 RT."

Unabi's antioxidant properties are linked to the vitamin C and R-active substances it contains. Unabi fruits are a unique source of vitamin C, containing 246.7-485.7 mg/100 g, which is 20-40 times more than in apples and 5-10 times more than in citrus fruits. The best varieties accumulating more than 400 mg/100 g of vitamin C are "Jishin-zao" (485.7 mg/100 g), "Shiyang-zao" (462.1 mg/100 g), and "Jun-zao" (418.1 mg/100 g) (Fig. 1). The amount of vitamin C in Unabi fruits is determined as mg/100 g depending on the variety characteristics.

Table 1. The amount of R-active substances in the fruits of Chilonjiyda.

Sort	Catechins, mg/100 g	Leukoanthocyanins, mg/100 g	Flavonoids, mg/100 g
Ta-Yan-Szao	41,7	32,7	13,0
Shiyang-zao	108,0	32,0	17,5
Zanxuang-da-zao	37,2	38,5	10,2
Tang-zao	57,2	27,4	13,0
Maya-bayi-zao	23,6	15,7	8,6
Jun-zao	113,4	39,3	11,4
Dabay-ling-zao	24,3	16,1	8,7
Dong-zao	25,9	33,6	10,2
Linyu-li-zao	25,9	17,6	16,6
Jishin-zao	181,0	28,8	14,7

Chilonjiyda mevalaridagi fenolik birikmalar β -faol katexinlar, leykoantotsianinlar va flavonollarni o'z ichiga oladi. Nav farqlari katexin miqdorida eng aniq bo'lib, 23,6 dan 181 mg/100 g gacha (1-jadval).

"Jishin-zao", "Jun-zao" va "Shiyang-zao" chilonjiyda navlari 100 mg/100 g dan ortiq miqdorda to'playdi. Leykoantotsianin miqdori chilonjiyda nav xususiyatlariga qarab 1,5-2 baravar o'zgaradi, "Jun-zao", "Zanxuang-da-zao" va "Dong-zao" navlarida leykoantotsianinlar ustunlik qiladi. Flavonol miqdori esa 8,6 dan 17,5 mg/100 g gacha diapazonda o'zgarib turdi va eng yuqori ko'rstkichlar "Shiyang-zao", "Linyu-li-zao", "Tang-zao" navlariga mos ravishda 17,5; 16,6; 13,0; tegishli bo'ldi. Minerals are actively involved in metabolism and are considered essential trace elements (Table 2):

Table 2. Mineral composition of jujube fruits.

Sort	Potassium, mg/100 g	Sodium, mg/100 g	Calcium, mg/100 g	Magnesium, mg/100g	Iron, mg/100g
Ta-Yan-Szao	222,8	32,4	37,3	25,6	0,61
Shiyang-zao	413,9	50,2	31,9	23,1	0,64
Zanxuang-da-zao	175,7	21,6	37,2	26,1	0,71
Tang-zao	361,1	43,1	22,9	15,3	0,83
Maya-bayi-zao	178,6	22,1	37,7	26,0	0,81
Jun-zao	522,1	53,5	45,1	29,2	0,84
Dabay-ling-zao	179,7	23,1	38,2	26,1	0,84
Dong-zao	350,1	50,7	52,9	26,7	0,76
Linyu-li-zao	285,7	40,1	37,2	24,9	0,71

Jishin-zao	536,1	54,6	46,8	33,3	0,87
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Potassium is necessary for the functioning of the heart muscle; sodium regulates the water balance in the body; calcium participates in the structure of bone tissue; magnesium is a component of a number of enzymes; iron participates in blood formation. The fruits of the studied Unabi varieties contain a large amount of these important macro and microelements (Table 3). The "Jishin-zao" and "Jun-zao" varieties were characterized by maximum mineral accumulation: potassium (536.1–522.1 mg/100 g), sodium (54.6–53.5 mg/100 g), calcium (46.8–45.1 mg/100 g), magnesium (33.3–29.2 mg/100 g), and iron (0.87–0.84 mg/100 g).

Conclusion. Unabi fruits have been proven to be a source of functional nutrient components: vitamin C (246.1-476.7 mg/100g), R-active substances (catechins 23.6-181.0 mg/100g), leucoanthocyanins (15.-39.3 mg/100g), and 5 essential amino acids and minerals: potassium (175.7-536.1 mg/100g), magnesium (15.3-26.7 mg/100g), calcium (22.9-46.8 mg/100g), and iron (0.61-0.87%). Due to their high content of components and beneficial properties, it is recommended to consume them fresh.

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